

SIMULTANEOUS ACQUISITION OF DATA ON REFRACTIVE INDEX, STRAIN, TEMPERATURE AND CROSS-LINKING KINETICS

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SUMMARY

An Abbe refractometer was custom-modified to enable the simultaneous acquisition of data on refractive index via the refractometer and strain, temperature, refractive index and cross-linking kinetics via optical fibre sensors. The experiments were carried out isothermally at 50, 60 and 70 °C using an epoxy/amine resin system.

Keywords: Fibre optic sensor, Fresnel reflection, Refractive index, FTIR spectroscopy

INTRODUCTION

A number of optical fibre-based process monitoring techniques are available for characterising the rate and degree of cross-linking of thermosetting resins [1]. In situations where qualitative information is required, the increase in the cross-link density of the resin system can be tracked by monitoring its refractive index. As the molecular weight of the resin system increases with the formation of cross-links, the density also increases. Previous researchers have demonstrated the use of optical fibre sensors to monitor refractive index during the cross-linking of thermosetting resins [2]. The two main methods employed involved using a de-clad portion of an optical fibre [2] or using a cleaved optical fibre that serves as a Fresnel reflector [3]. In the former case, a 20 mm portion of cladding was removed from a high refractive index core optical fibre. Epoxy resin was introduced to the region of the exposed fibre core and the transmitted intensity from a laser was monitored. As the cross-linking reaction progressed, a decrease in intensity was recorded. The second method was based on the Fresnel reflection at the interface between the core of a cleaved optical fibre and an epoxy resin system. It was found that the changes in the reflected light intensity were linear functions of the temperature. Thus the change in the density (and therefore refractive index) with temperature was also linear. Previous to these, a method was used whereby a cured cylindrical piece of epoxy resin acted as a light guide between two standard silica fibres [4]. The sensor assembly was embedded in the resin sample and the intensity monitored during the cross-linking process. A decrease in intensity was observed during the reaction as the refractive index of the resin approached that of the cured epoxy fibre. In the case of the Fresnel reflection sensor, the reflection from a cleaved optical fibre offers a simple and low-cost route to monitor the refractive index of the thermosetting resin surrounding the fibre [1]. Besides these changes in refractive index, it is generally appreciated that when covalent bonds are formed during the cross-

linking process, the resin system shrinks. Furthermore, these cross-linking reactions are exothermic [5]. Therefore, in addition to monitoring the refractive index to infer the rate and extent of reaction, data on the temperature, shrinkage strain and cross-linking kinetics are desirable. Where quantitative data are required, this can be achieved by monitoring the depletion/formation of functional groups in the resin system. Infrared spectroscopy is used routinely to identify specified chemical functional groups.

Although a wide range of optical fibre-based sensor systems are available, cross-comparison between the various sensing techniques is not straightforward because:

- (a) The resin can be contained in different holders or substrates, such as metal or glass. Therefore, the possibility of surface-catalysed reactions cannot be ignored.
- (b) A key point to note with chemical kinetics is that it is important to control and monitor the temperature of the reaction vessel. As temperature is a key controlling factor for the rate of chemical reactions, it is important to ensure an identical thermal environment when experiments are conducted using different heating methods.
- (c) There is also a need to differentiate between quantitative and qualitative data. For example, spectral-based techniques can give quantitative data. Where qualitative data are used for monitoring the cross-linking process, it is necessary to establish the cross-correlation with quantitative techniques to give confidence to end-users who may be interested in intensity-based and cost-effective monitoring techniques.

A primary advantage of the simultaneous technique reported in this paper is that the parameters of interest are monitored under identical processing conditions. Thus cross-correlation studies between the techniques can be performed with a high degree of confidence. Optical fibre sensors offer a number of advantages including the following: (i) immunity to electromagnetic interference; (ii) they can be multiplexed; (iii) easy integration into composite performs; and (iv) remote monitoring is possible. Moreover, optical fibre-based sensors can be designed to be qualitative or quantitative and can be used to define when the cross-linking reaction is complete. This will enable processing equipment to be switched off when the cross-linking reaction has reached its required degree of conversion, leading to significant cost-savings in energy consumption.

An Abbe refractometer is commonly used to measure the refractive indices of liquids. In the current paper, an Abbe refractometer was used as a platform to obtain uniform temperature and to enable comparison with optical fibre-based refractive index measurements. The Abbe refractometer was modified to accommodate the following fibre optic sensors: (i) a single-fibre transmission sensor to enable the acquisition of quantitative data on the cross-linking kinetics via transmission Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy; (ii) Fresnel reflection sensors to monitor the refractive index; and (iii) fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors to monitor the combined effects of shrinkage strain and temperature during the cross-linking of an epoxy/amine resin system.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sensors and Materials

[A] Sensors: The sensors used in this study were fabricated in-house. Details of the individual sensors are given below:

(i) Single-fibre transmission sensor for the acquisition of near-infrared spectra: Multi-mode step-index optical fibres (Aomolin Photoelectrical Technology Co. Ltd., China) with core and cladding diameters of 105 and 125 μm respectively, were used.

(ii) Fresnel reflection sensor: Two types of Fresnel reflection sensors were used. One type employed multi-mode step-index optical fibres (supplier as mentioned above). The second type was fabricated using single-mode optical fibres (SMF-28TM, Corning[®], US) with core and cladding diameters of 8.2 and 125 μm respectively.

(iii) Fibre Bragg grating sensor: Single-mode photo-sensitive fibres (PS1500, Fibercore Ltd., UK) with core and cladding diameters of 10 and 125 μm respectively, were used.

[B] Epoxy-amine resin system: The thermosetting epoxy-amine resin system used was Araldite LY3505/XB3403 (Huntsman Advanced Materials, UK). The two main components of LY3505 epoxy resin were bisphenol-A and bisphenol-F. The XB3403 amine-based hardener was polyoxypropylene diamine. The resin and hardener were mixed thoroughly in the stoichiometric ratio of 100:35 (resin:hardener) by weight, followed by degassing in a vacuum chamber at 70 kPa for 20 minutes. The resin system was injected into a “cell” (housed in the Abbe refractometer) via a syringe and heated from 30 °C to isothermal temperatures of 50 °C, 60 °C and 70 °C. A new batch of the resin system was prepared for each experiment.

Abbe Refractometer and Sensor Integration

Abbe refractometer: Since it was not desirable to cross-link the thermosetting resin directly on the prisms of the Abbe refractometer (High Accuracy 60/ED, Bellingham & Stanley, UK), a pair of glass slides were used to construct a “cell” to contain the resin system (Figure 1a). The bottom slide (positioned on the lower prism of the refractometer) was custom-made (SF-14, Schott, Germany) to have the same refractive index as the refractometer prisms ($n = 1.76$). A contact liquid (monobromonaphthalene, Bellingham & Stanley, UK) was used between the custom-made slide and the lower prism of the refractometer to ensure good optical transmission between them. A 1 mm polytetrafluoroethylene spacer was used to separate the bottom slide from a standard borosilicate glass slide, and to contain the resin system. Release agent (Frekote[®] 700-NC, Loctite[®], US) was applied to the surface of both slides for easy removal of the resin after processing. Once all of the sensors were secured on the custom-made slide, the borosilicate glass slide was placed on top of the spacers. Silicone rubber adhesive (494-118, RS, UK) was used to seal the glass slides with the spacer, and this cell was left overnight at room temperature to enable the silicone adhesive to cross-link. The pre-mixed and de-gassed resin system was introduced into the cell via a syringe and needle. The Abbe refractometer was operated in reflection mode using a sodium lamp which emitted monochromatic light at 589 nm. The temperature of the prisms was controlled by circulating water from a temperature-controlled water bath (TE10D Tempette[®], Techne, US). Prior to conducting the cross-linking experiments, the temperature profile in the cell was measured using 15 thermocouples and the LY3505 resin.

Sensor integration: An overview of the instrumentation and sensor interrogation systems used in this study is shown in Figure 1b. A schematic illustration of the experimental set-up is shown in Figure 2. The following sensors were secured to the inner wall of the custom-made slide using a UV-curable resin (UV403-T, Shanghai Jiyuan Ltd., China): (i) a fibre optic transmission sensor to enable the acquisition of

near-infrared spectra of the cross-linking resin (Figure 2i); (ii) a Fresnel reflection sensor to monitor the refractive index of the resin during the cross-linking reaction (Figure 2ii); (iii) a fibre Bragg grating sensor (Figure 2iii) to monitor the shrinkage strain of the resin during cross-linking; and (iv) a K-type thermocouple.

Figure 1 (a) A cross-sectional schematic of the custom-made cell on the Abbe refractometer. (b) An overview of the systems used to interrogate the sensors.

Details of each of the above-mentioned sensors are given below:

(i) *Single-fibre transmission sensor*: Two cleaved multi-mode optical fibres were housed in a fused silica precision-bore capillary fixture and the cleaved end-faces were secured approximately 50 μm apart. The sensor was coupled to the light source and detector of a Fourier transform infra-red (FTIR) spectrometer (Bruker MATRIX™-F duplex (Bruker Optics Ltd., UK)). The spectrometer was programmed to operate in the near-infrared region between 11000 and 4000 cm^{-1} . Spectra were collected at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 64 scans.

(ii) *Fresnel reflection sensor*: A single-mode optical fibre was used to transmit light from a 1550 nm modular laser diode (ILX Lightwave, USA). The fibre was connected, via a custom-made 2x2 coupler, to an InGaAs photodiode detector (Thorlabs, UK). In order to increase the signal-to-noise ratio, the detector was connected to a photodiode amplifier (PDA 200, Laser 2000, UK) and a low-noise preamplifier (SR560, SRS, UK). The two distal cleaved ends of the sensor were secured adjacent to one another on the custom-made slide. During the cross-linking reaction, the reflected signal from the fibre core/resin interface was recorded using a data acquisition system (National Instruments, UK). In addition to single-mode fibres, multi-mode fibres were also used as Fresnel sensors. In this instance, a separate interrogation unit was used where the sensor was connected to a halogen light source (Ocean optics, HL-2000) and a photodiode detector (APD module C5460) through a custom-made 2x2 coupler. The signal from the detector was recorded using LabVIEW software.

(iii) *Fibre Bragg grating sensor*: A photo-sensitive Germania-Boron (Ge-B) co-doped single-mode fibre was used for fabricating fibre Bragg gratings (FBGs). The gratings were inscribed on the core of the fibre using the phase mask technique and an excimer laser (Braggstar, Coherent Inc., UK) operating at 248 nm. The Bragg gratings were produced using a pulse energy of 10 mJ and a pulse frequency of 20 Hertz. FBG spectra were recorded using an IS 7000 FBG Interrogation System (FibrePro, UK).

Figure 2 A schematic illustration of the location of the various sensors on the Abbe refractometer: (i) Single-fibre transmission sensor; (ii) Fresnel reflection sensor; (iii) Fibre Bragg grating sensor; and (iv) thermocouple.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Abbe refractometer: As it was necessary to introduce the cell to the Abbe refractometer, it was essential to assess the effects of the cell, the release agent and the contact liquid on the refractive index measurements. This was evaluated using standard refractive index oils in the range 1.52 to 1.58 (RF/18005, Cargille Labs, US). Figure 3 shows a linear relationship between the manufacturer-stated refractive index values and the refractometer-measured values of the oils. This suggests that the influence of the cell on the operation of the refractometer was negligible. These experiments were also carried out, using a reference standard with a refractive index of 1.56, from ambient to 70 °C in increments of 10 °C. A repeatable linear relationship was observed between the temperature and the measured refractive index.

Fresnel reflection sensor: The intensity of the light reflected at normal incidence from the cleaved ends of the Fresnel reflection sensor fibres was used to infer the changes in the refractive index of the resin during cross-linking. The Fresnel reflection coefficient is a function of the difference between the refractive indices of the fibre core and the surrounding cross-linking resin for a perpendicular-cleaved fibre. The Fresnel reflection coefficient can be expressed as:

$$R = \left(\frac{n_{core} - n_{resin}}{n_{core} + n_{resin}} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where n_{core} and n_{resin} are the refractive indices of the fibre core and the surrounding resin respectively. Figure 4 shows the response from a pair of single-mode and multi-mode optical fibre Fresnel sensors for the LY3505/XB3403 resin system that was cross-linked at 60 °C. The Fresnel reflection data were normalised to the initial measurement at 30 °C. It is clear that the signals obtained using single-mode and multi-mode fibre sensors are comparable. A similar trend was observed when the resin system was cross-linked at 50 and 70 °C. However, it was observed that the long-term stability of the single-mode fibre sensor setup was more repeatable and therefore the single-mode optical fibre Fresnel sensor configuration was used for the remainder of this study.

Figure 3

Figure 3 Measured (Abbe refractometer) and manufacturer-stated refractive index values for the reference refractive indices liquids.

Figure 4

Figure 4 Fresnel reflection data during cross-linking of LY3505/XB3403 at 60 °C obtained using single-mode and multi-mode optical fibre sensors.

Comparisons between the Fresnel reflection signal and the refractometer-measured refractive indices at 50, 60 and 70 °C are shown in Figures 5 (a, b and c). It is clear that the trends between the refractometer (conventional) and optical fibre-based methods are similar. Since the experiments were carried out simultaneously, the temperature regime is identical, and therefore it is reasonable that the refractive indices measured by the conventional and optical fibre techniques will be similar. With reference to Figures 5 (a, b and c), the initial drop in the amplitude of the Fresnel reflection signal can be attributed to a decrease in the refractive index of the resin system as it is heated from 30 °C to the isothermal temperature (50, 60 or 70 °C). The subsequent gradual increase in the reflected light intensity relates to the isothermal stage, whereby an increase in the density and molecular weight of the resin due to cross-linking cause an increase in the refractive index [1, 6]. The subsequent stabilisation of the reflected light intensity suggests retardation of the rate of cross-linking.

Figure 5 A comparison between the Fresnel reflection signal and the refractive index (Abbe refractometer) at processing temperatures of (a) 50 °C; (b) 60 °C and (c) 70 °C.

Figure 6 (a) Spectra of LY3505/XB3403 resin system obtained using the transmission sensor during the cross-linking reaction at 60 °C. The inset shows a generalised reaction scheme for an epoxy/amine resin system. (b) The degree of conversion of the epoxy functional group when cross-linked at 50, 60 and 70 °C.

Single-fibre transmission sensor: A single-fibre transmission sensor was used to obtain near-FTIR spectra of the resin system as a function of cross-linking time at specified isothermal temperatures. The evolution of FTIR spectra during the cross-linking of the resin system at 60 °C is presented in Figure 6a. The epoxy and amine chemical species react upon the application of heat to form a highly cross-linked structure. During the reaction the primary amine (NH₂) first reacts with the epoxy group, whereby a hydrogen atom on the amine is transferred to an oxygen atom on the epoxy group. This is effectively the formation of a covalent bond between the epoxy and the amine with the additional formation of a new functional group (hydroxyl (OH) group). This new species retains a reactive hydrogen atom which can react with a further epoxy molecule. In Figure 6a, the absorbance peak at 4933 cm⁻¹ was associated with the fundamental vibrations of the primary amine group, and the peak at 4530 cm⁻¹ was attributed to the epoxy CH₂ and C-H deformation bands [6]. The depletion of these peak areas is caused by the epoxy/amine reaction as shown in the inset in Figure 6a. The peak at 4621 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the combination bands of the C-H stretching vibration of the aromatic ring in the epoxy resin [6]. The area of this peak does not change as a function of time during the cross-linking reaction because the functional group does not participate in the reaction. Therefore this peak area can be used to normalise those of the epoxy and amine absorbance bands. The conversion of the functional group of interest (epoxy or amine) can be calculated from Figure 6a using the following relationship:

$$\alpha = 1 - \left(\frac{A_x/A_{CH}}{A_x/A_{CH}} \right)_t / \left(\frac{A_x/A_{CH}}{A_x/A_{CH}} \right)_0 \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where α is the conversion of the reacting group (amine or epoxy), A_x is the area of the absorption peak of the functional group of interest, A_{CH} represents the area of the reference C-H peak, t specifies the cross-linking reaction time in minutes and 0 is the start of the reaction [6]. Figure 6b illustrates typical plots of epoxy functional group conversions from cross-linking experiments carried out at 50, 60 and 70 °C, calculated using Equation 2. It can be observed that epoxy groups are consumed at a faster rate at higher isothermal temperatures. The overall epoxy conversion is seen to be greater when the resin was held at a higher temperature; 96% at 70 °C and ~93% at 50 °C.

Figure 7 A comparison of epoxy conversion (FTIR spectroscopy) data and Fresnel reflection data for the LY3505/XB3403 resin system at 50, 60 and 70 °C.

Figures 7 (a, b and c) demonstrate clearly that the trends in the data for the Fresnel reflection coefficients are similar to those obtained via the single-fibre transmission sensor. Therefore, accepting the limitation of intensity-based sensor systems, it can be concluded that the low-cost Fresnel sensor can be used to track the progress of the cross-linking resin system. In this experiment the data acquisition systems were initiated manually. This may account for the discrepancy seen in Figure 7c. In instances where quantitative data are required on the cross-linking process, the single-fibre transmission sensor is a viable solution. However, it does dictate the need for a FTIR spectrometer. In situations where the temperature of the reaction vessel is known, this study has demonstrated that the Fresnel sensor (cleaved optical fibre) will suffice to monitor the rate of cross-linking.

Figure 8a illustrates the response of the FBG sensor when the resin was heated from 30 °C to 70 °C and held for 20 hours. Although further analysis needs to be completed, initial observations are outlined here. The response of the FBG sensor during the cross-linking reaction was attributed to two factors – strain induced by shrinkage of the resin and temperature variation. Initially, the ramp in temperature from 30 °C to 70 °C induces a shift in the Bragg reflection peak of 0.34 nm, towards a longer wavelength as the grating expands. The shift of the Bragg wavelength $\Delta\lambda_B$ due to temperature change ΔT and external strain ε can be expressed as:

$$[\Delta\lambda_B]_{\varepsilon,T} = [\Delta\lambda_B]_{\varepsilon} + [\Delta\lambda_B]_T = \alpha\Delta\varepsilon + \beta\Delta T \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha = \lambda_B(1 - \rho_e)$; ρ_e (~ 0.74) [7]) is the strain-optic constant of the Ge-B co-doped fibre [8]; and $\beta = (\alpha_\Lambda + \alpha_n)\Delta T$; α_Λ and α_n are the coefficients of thermal expansion and temperature-optic respectively. In Figure 8a the temperature sensitivity was calculated from the initial heating phase (strain-free) to be $9.2 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$. For this temperature change of $\sim 32^\circ\text{C}$, $[\Delta\lambda_B]_T$ was 0.294 nm . During the cool-down phase, $[\Delta\lambda_B]_{e,T}$ was 0.599 nm over a temperature change of $\sim 32^\circ\text{C}$. The residual compressive strain at a temperature of 33°C after cooling was calculated to be $263 \mu\epsilon$.

Figure 8 (a) FBG response during cross-linking at 70°C and subsequent cooling to ambient. (b) Change in the Bragg peak reflection and epoxy conversion (FTIR spectroscopy) during cross-linking at 70°C . (c) Change in the Bragg peak reflection and Fresnel reflection during cross-linking at 70°C .

Figure 8b shows the correlation between the change in the Bragg peak wavelength as the epoxy conversion rises. This is primarily attributed to shrinkage of the resin system as described above. A similar trend is observed with the Fresnel reflection sensor data (Figure 8c).

CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility of using an Abbe refractometer in conjunction with a custom-made cell and optical fibre sensors to simultaneously obtain qualitative *and* quantitative information on: (i) rate of heating; (ii) refractive index; (iii) Fresnel reflection coefficient; (iv) rate and degree of conversion of reactive functional groups; and (v) shrinkage strain. The performance of the modified refractometer was assessed using standard refractive index oils. A negligible effect was found on the operation of the refractometer as a consequence of the presence of the custom-made cell that was located between the prisms of the refractometer. Although not shown in this paper, excellent correlation was obtained between conventional FTIR spectroscopy and the single-fibre transmission sensor data. During the isothermal cross-linking of LY3505/XB3403, similar trends were observed between the single-fibre transmission sensor and the fibre optic Fresnel reflection sensor. This paper has demonstrated that the low-cost-Fresnel sensor can be used to track the cross-linking behaviour. The FBG sensors indicated a compressive cure strain of $263 \mu\epsilon$ at 70°C . Further analysis is in progress.

The use of these inexpensive optical fibre sensors allows the cross-linking kinetics of thermosetting resin systems to be monitored, and thus allows the cross-linking process to be optimised. These sensor designs can also be used for integrity monitoring of engineering materials and structures.

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